

Open@RIT Position Paper: Accessibility Issues in Federal Grant Funding

Stephen Jacobs, Director, Open@RIT, [ORCID](#)

Kripa Kundaliya, Researcher, Open@RIT, [ORCID](#)

Introduction:

Persons with disabilities (PWDs) are considered the largest minority in the nation and in the world [1] [2] [3], but only a few group policies and procedures from agencies, directorates, or funding programs address accessibility support in federally funded research efforts and convenings. There are a wide variety of support types available, and each has different requirements, processes, deadlines, and restrictions. This lack of standardization can make it difficult to acquire the necessary support for PWDs by placing the onus on PWDs to navigate complex and unique application processes for the same support.

In this opinion paper, we propose the development of a standardized support mechanism across all federally funded research to provide access and accommodations for individuals with disabilities as they conduct research and disseminate their work through conferences and convenings. This could be implemented by mandated policy across agencies, by an entity that handles all post-award and conference requests for accessibility and accommodations or another, similar effort.

Problem Statement:

Deaf/hard-of-hearing(DHH), Blind/low-vision (BLV), and other differently-abled academicians, senior personnel, students, and post-doctoral fellows engaged in federally-funded research face challenges in acquiring accommodations for accessibility. These include, but are not limited to:

- Human-provided ASL-English interpreting and interview transcription services for the DHH and non-DHH participants
- Visual and Pro-tactile interpreting/descriptive services for the BLV participants
- Adaptive lab equipment and computing peripherals
- Accessibility support or remediation for physical sites

These supports are necessary for the research effort's home site to ensure full participation in research meetings, professional conferences, and other "off-site" research and dissemination activities. Having these services available is important for promoting an inclusive research environment on a larger scale.

Current Policies and Practices:

Principal Investigators (PIs) who request support for accessibility-related accommodations are often required to apply for such funding in their initial grant proposals, and this approach has several flaws.

First and foremost, this funding process reduces the direct application of research dollars for these PIs and their teams compared to other researchers applying for similar amounts in the same program. Simply put, if two applicants are applying for a \$100,000 grant, and one needs to fund \$10,000 worth of accommodations, services, and equipment out of these funds, they comparatively have \$10,000 less to pursue the proposed research activities.

Second, it can be limiting for the funded project to work with or hire differently-abled co-PIs, students, or postdocs once the initial award has been made. In this case, PIs then have to reallocate research dollars meant for other uses within the grant to support such accommodations or find other funding to support those needs within their institution.

Some agencies have programs for post-award supplemental funding to address these challenges. While these are well-intentioned, many are problematic. One major challenge is that supplemental funding may only be available if a given program has enough remaining budget. If a given year's allocation has been expended on the initial awards for the solicitation, there may be no money left to support accommodations. What's more, the sheer number of different programs adds more challenges.

The table below briefly illustrates the range of variability across a subset of representative supplemental funding programs. These highlighted programs and processes only represent a sample of the various programs PWDs have to navigate.

Each program is linked in the top row of the table for access to the complete program information. Beyond this table, more extensive lists of NSF and NIH offerings are provided by those agencies. These include the NSF [PWDChart](#) and the NIH [Grants Guide](#).

Program	<u>NSF STEM Access for Persons with Disabilities (STEM-APWD)</u>	<u>NIH Grants Guide (Alt Link)</u>	<u>NSF PAPPG FASED</u>	<u>NIH Support for Scientific Conferences (R13 and U13)</u>	<u>US - NSF BIO MCB Guide Proposals</u>
Streamlined process	No	No	Yes	No	No
Specifically focused on Accessibility/A ccommodation	Yes	No	Yes	No	No
Application and award timeline	2 months before the funds are needed.	3-4 months from application to award. 10-month window for applying - October to May	If part of the PAPPG, same as the proposal date. If supplemental 2 months.	8-9 months from application to award	Part of a full event proposal
Funding Caps?	Yes, \$100,000.	Variable	Must not be a major component of the total budget.	Variable	Conferences \$5,000 to \$20,000 Workshops, \$50,000 to \$100,000
Conf Support Only?	No	No	No	Yes	Yes
Submitted by PI	Yes or by eligible organizations on behalf of PIs	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes
Special Procedures/Approvals?	Yes	Yes	Yes	Yes	No

Identifying and Acquiring Services

There seem to be sufficient guides available for identifying hardware and software support. However, understanding the breadth and depth of issues surrounding human services support is more complex and outside the experience of most PIs.

Take the case of interpretation services for DHH researchers and/or conference participants and attendees. Needs vary from person to person and case to case. One full-time researcher may need a full-time ASL interpretation on-site, while another might prefer to work primarily through digital text channels, only requiring interpretation for staff meetings and other group activities.

Convenings provide a greater challenge. A DHH researcher who attends a conference is often provided interpreting or captioning services for sessions only. This excludes them from conversations outside of sessions, both formally planned and spontaneous ones, before, during, or after official sessions. Should a group of DHH researchers wish to attend different sessions or meetings, the conveners may not have provided enough interpreters to support those opportunities.

Proposed Solutions:

Research Support: We recommend implementing a straightforward and efficient process with dedicated funds to support differently-abled PIs, co-PIs, postdocs, or students involved in federally-funded research endeavors. This initiative would be post-award, with eligibility based on the initial grant award notification. PIs would be flexible in applying for these funds at any stage during the grant period to support research activities or dissemination efforts. Ideally, such a process would be established at the top level of individual agencies or standardized across all federal agencies overseeing federally funded research. Comprehensive guidelines and directories of service and equipment providers would be made available to facilitate this process.

Individuals seeking funding for accessibility-related accommodations should have the opportunity to apply directly upon notification of the grant award and throughout the grant's duration, supported by a signature from a PI or a sponsored research staff member from an institute of higher education. Those not initially named in the grant application should complete requisite forms detailing their specific needs, with a co-signature from a PI or co-PI.

The process should be straightforward and focus purely on evaluating the need & provision of accessibility resources, considering that the grant has already been secured and the PIs have endorsed the individuals requesting funds for equipment or

services. Participants should be allowed to request funds multiple times within the grant period, as the need for attendance at events like training or conferences may arise unexpectedly.

Funds allocated for procuring equipment or services would flow through the PI's institution and follow their standard purchasing or contracting procedures. In cases where funding for services remains unused upon a participant's departure from the project, they should be able to transfer those funds to another federally funded effort, ensuring efficient resource use.

Conference Support: Based on the population size, conference planners should assume that people with disabilities will participate as presenters or attendees at the event and ensure that their events will provide appropriate resources for their support. Funding from the supporting federal agencies should be made available to provide the necessary accommodations. Research should be conducted to determine what the base support of service providers and accommodations should be based on a given conference or convening's size. The event organizers should be able to apply for additional support, provided a participant's request is made within a stated time before the event. For example, stipulate a deadline of six weeks to request supplemental accommodation so that the organizers can acquire what's needed within 30 days of the event.

Potential Implementation Outcomes

At a minimum, more differently-abled individuals will be able to participate or have their participation improved in federally funded research, and PIs will be less challenged and better supported to bring differently-abled subject-matter experts into the research and dissemination process. By providing clear, uniform policies and practices across all federally supported research and related dissemination activities, Open Science becomes truly accessible.

Acknowledgments:

The roots of this effort began when the author and Dr. Mel Chua received funding for their research as part of the first Critical Digital Infrastructure research cohort and were able to negotiate for accessibility support services outside their award. Others who provided input are

- Dr. Liz Hare, Quantitative Geneticist, Dog Genetics LLC
- Dr. Mel Chua, Independent Researcher
- Dr. Christopher Kurz, Professor and Director of Mathematics and Science Language and Learning Lab, National Technical Institute for the Deaf

- Michael Nolan, Associate Director, Open@RIT
- Christopher Baker, Assistant Director, Open@RIT

References:

[1] Disability Stats and Facts

<https://www.disabilityfunders.org/disability-stats-and-facts>

[2] Diverse Perspectives: People with Disabilities Fulfilling Your Business Goals

<https://www.dol.gov/agencies/odep/publications/fact-sheets/diverse-perspectives-people-with-disabilities-fulfilling-your-business-goals#:~:text=As%20the%20nation%27s%20largest%20minority,their%20workforce%20and%20customer%20base.>

[3] One billion people with disabilities: the world's biggest minority!

<https://www.hi-canada.org/en/one-billion-people-with-disabilities-the-world-s-biggest-minority>